

**A CRITICAL COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE NATIONAL
ACCREDITATION STANDARDS FOR HOSPITALS OF INDIA,
AUSTRALIA, DENMARK AND SOUTH AFRICA**

Research proposal for the admission of

Doctor of Letters (D. Litt.) Degree By

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Introduction:

Quality has become a fundamental requirement for healthcare organizations in order to survive and succeed in the competitive, demanding and challenging healthcare service industry. Total Quality Management (TQM) is considered to be an essential way to achieve the required excellence in business practice, as it provides customer satisfaction through continuous quality improvement. TQM is a promising management approach which focuses on the customers, improvement of the structures, processes and outcome. The implementation of TQM concepts is a world-wide phenomenon in all sectors and industries for-improving the quality of services offered, reducing the cost, gaining the trust of customers, attracting the new customers and sustaining in the competitive market environment.

In this modern era of science, technology and quality, the healthcare service industry is a thriving sector, which is continuously on high demand in all the continents of the world. The healthcare service industry is decades behind when compared to other industries in terms of creating safer systems. Today, developed and developing nations are working towards continuous quality improvement and patient safety by achieving the national and or international healthcare accreditation and providing safe, effective, patient-centred, timely, efficient and equitable health care services to all their patients and families. These national and or international healthcare accrediting organizations do follow the principles of TQM to improve quality and patient safety.

Even where healthcare systems are well developed and resourced, there is clear evidence that quality remains a serious concern, with expected outcomes, not predictably achieved and with wide variations in standards of healthcare delivery within and between healthcare systems. In every country, there is an opportunity to improve the quality and performance of the healthcare system, as well as growing awareness and public pressure to do so. The use of accreditation in various countries does not follow a standardized methodology, and therefore the results achieved by each country are not always directly comparable.¹

Accreditation of a health care organization is an external evaluation of the level of compliance against a set of organizational standards². The United States (US) American College of Surgeons (ACS), first developed quality standards for hospitals & other health care facilities and introduced the “Minimum Standard for Hospitals” in 1917. Increased world trade in manufactured goods after the World War II, leads to the creation of the Geneva, Switzerland based International Standards Organization (ISO) in 1947. In 1951 the Joint Commission on Accreditation of Healthcare Organizations (JCAHO) was formed in the United States.³ This concept was exported to Canada and Australia in the 1960s and 1970s and reached Europe in the 1980s. Accreditation programs spread all over the world in the 1990s.⁴

The healthcare accreditation is usually a voluntary program, sponsored by a Non-Governmental Organization (NGO), in which educated, experienced and trained personnel

evaluate the compliance of a health care organization with pre-established performance standards.⁵

Healthcare accreditation standards are advocated as an important means of improving structure, process and outcome. The accrediting organizations assert that their methodologies are effective and efficient in improving the structure, process, outcome and maintaining the quality of the healthcare industry.

Now, most health care managers and policy makers review & evaluate and control and improve in quality, as an imperative⁶. Therefore, with this demand for improved quality, a growing interest and expansion in accreditation programs has occurred worldwide during the past decade⁷. In a variety of industries, accreditation is recognized as a symbol of quality indicating that the organization meets certain performance standards⁸, and provides an opportunity for that organization to evaluate their operation against national standards⁹.

Today, we have various national accrediting organizations for hospitals all over the world. These healthcare accrediting organizations have developed their own set of standards, which are accredited by the Ireland based International Society for Quality in Health Care (ISQua), which is the only organization to 'accredit the accreditors'.
However, when we compare critically with the national accreditation standards (ISQua accredited) of the countries in all the continents of the world, there are variations in the number, names of the chapters, number of standards and evidence of compliance or measurable elements of the standards. Despite of the common needs, glitches and errors in the healthcare service industry all over the world, we have different sets of healthcare standards for the hospitals accredited by ISQua. Moreover, till date no one has even thought about having a unique set of healthcare standards applicable for all the general hospitals of the world.
The researcher has considered the seven-continent model for this research study, which is usually taught in China, India, the Philippines, parts of Western Europe and most English-speaking countries, including Australia ¹⁰ and England. ¹¹

Significance of the problem:

Healthcare is the fundamental need and right of every single human being on this planet. The healthcare quality needs are the same all over the world, and providing the quality healthcare services is the vision of each public and private healthcare service provider, for which they follow the National and or International Healthcare Accreditation Standards for their hospitals. Unfortunately, the World Health Organization (WHO), who monitors the health issues in the public sector of the world doesn't have a unique, comprehensive set of hospital quality standards applicable, available and accessible for all general hospitals in the private and public sectors of the the world till date.

1. There are **variations in the chapters** of National Healthcare Accreditation Standards for hospitals.
2. There are **variations in the standards** (and content) of National Healthcare Accreditation Standards for hospitals.
3. There is **variation in the sub-standards or measurable elements** of National Healthcare Accreditation Standards.
4. At present there is **no unique, comprehensive set of hospital quality standards applicable, available and accessible** for all general hospitals in the world.

Objectives:

1. To identify the main distinguishing attributes in the selected national healthcare accreditation standards for hospitals in India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa.
2. Compare and analyse critically the national healthcare accreditation standards for hospitals in India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa.
3. To propose an outline of “The Universal Healthcare Quality Standards for General Hospitals”.

Review of Literature:

The increased international focus on improving patient outcomes, safety and quality of care has led stakeholders, policy makers and healthcare provider organizations adopt standardized processes for evaluating health care organizations.¹² The World Health Organization has published several documents, policies on quality since 1990, but hasn't published the standards for the hospitals till now.¹³ Patient safety and patient centred care are emerging as key drivers in health care reform.¹⁴

In the related literature, accreditation brings the idea of an easy-to-understand and feasible methodology, as it uses medical terminology. It addresses the appropriate conduct commonly known by the professionals in the practice, guiding, however, towards an optimal organization, which standardizes the procedures to allow the creation of viable indicators of comparison and recommends the written recording of policies and procedures of the institution that has become a candidate to the process.¹⁵

Healthcare has become increasingly more complex, and with this increased complexity, the number of medical errors and adverse events has also increased, reaching an alarming level. Since the publication of the “To Err is Human report”,¹⁶ there has been a national drive towards addressing the hidden issue of medical errors and patient safety by examining their prevalence and underlying causes. Based on this premise, healthcare providers have implemented national and international healthcare accreditation standards in order to prevent errors. Advancements in technologies have included new safety features to ensure that medical errors ranging from the operating room to the charting of pharmaceutical information are minimized.¹⁷ Yet, even with these innovations and precautions, there have been no major improvements in the rate of medical errors.¹⁸

The current estimate of total annual deaths by medical errors in the United States is now 400, 000 in comparison to the previous estimate from 1999 of 44,000 to 98, 000 in the famous Institute of Medicine (IOM) report “to Err is Human”.¹⁹ Also, while minor changes have been made, there have been no major systematic changes to our healthcare system to prevent or to more efficiently detect harmful events or adverse events. However, the national and international accreditations reduced number of such errors.²⁰

The researcher will review all available and accessible literatures related to the research topic and objectives in research related text books, journals, articles, published research papers, all relevant government plans and reports, literature of external agencies, published academic literature and web portals etc. as per the objectives of this study.

Originality and expected contribution of the research:

The need for such research arises because there are variations in the national healthcare accreditation standards for hospitals of different countries from selected continents of the world, no one has conducted such a unique research till date and there are no universal standards for the general hospitals. Hence, the researcher will come up with an outline of “The Universal Healthcare Quality Standards for General Hospitals”. This study will be helpful to improve the NABH Standards of India and the rest of the countries in the world as well. Also, the WHO can adopt the proposed outline of the “The Universal Healthcare Quality Standards for General Hospitals”.

Limitations:

1. This research study is limited to one country from each continent of the globe with the highest GDP in that continent in the year 2018.²¹
2. This research study is limited to the national healthcare accreditation standards of selected countries from selected continents only.
3. This research study is limited to the latest edition of National Healthcare Accreditation Standards for Hospitals of selected countries which will be available on the registration date of this research proposal.
4. This research study is limited to the availability and accessibility of the national healthcare standards for hospitals of selected countries in English language only.
5. This research study is limited to the National Healthcare Accreditation Standards for Hospitals accredited by the Ireland based International Society for Quality in Health Care (ISQua).²²
6. The researcher has not selected any country from South America, North America and Antarctica continents as they did not fit into the sample selection criterion.

Research Methodology:

This is a systematic and empirical research study, which critically analyses the national healthcare accreditation standards for hospitals in India (National Accreditation Board For Hospitals and Healthcare Providers), Australia (National Safety and Quality Health Service Standards), Denmark (Danish Institute for Quality and Accreditation in Healthcare) and South Africa (COHSASA).

Sample Size:

The researcher has selected the sample based on the below selection criterion:

1. One country from each continent of the globe with highest GDP in that continent in the year 2018.
2. The selected country must have National Accreditation System or Program in English language which must be available and accessible.
3. The selected National Accreditation System or Program must be accredited by Ireland based International Society for Quality in Health Care (ISQua).

Hence, the researcher has selected the following countries as per the above selection criterion from each continent of the globe:

1. **India** is selected from Asia Continent,
2. **South Africa** is selected from Africa Continent,
3. **Denmark** is selected from Europe Continent
4. **Australia** is selected from Oceania or Australia Continent

Statement of Hypotheses:

1. Does the national healthcare accreditation standards for hospitals in India, Australia, Norway and South Africa are same?
2. Does the NABH (National Accreditation Board For Hospitals and Healthcare Providers) Standards of India are the best amongst the selected countries' Healthcare Standards for Hospitals?

Chapterisation:

1. The thesis consists of five chapters and an outline of "The Universal Healthcare Quality Standards for General Hospitals".

Chapter – I: Introduction

Chapter – II: Review of Literature

Chapter – III: Research Methodology

Chapter–IV: A Critical Comparative Study On National Accreditation Standards For Hospitals Of India, Australia, Denmark And South Africa

Chapter – V: Conclusion and Recommendations

Bibliography

Appendices

An outline of: The Universal Healthcare Quality Standards for General Hospitals.

Conclusions and Recommendations:

In this chapter the researcher will conclude his observations based on the critical analysis of his research and will recommend the Ministry of Health, India and the World Health Organization (WHO) for adopting “The Universal Healthcare Quality Standards for General Hospitals” to enhance the quality of general hospitals (public and private) of the world.

Expected outcome of the research:

The Universal Healthcare Quality Standards for General Hospitals will be applicable for all the general hospitals in all continents and countries of the world. Moreover, it will be a great help for NABH, WHO and ISQua to improve the NABH Standards, to develop the global standards for all the countries of the world and to standardize the ISQua accredited national standards respectively.

Advance the knowledge in the field of healthcare quality:

The Universal Healthcare Quality Standards for General Hospitals will be unique in the world which will be applicable for all the general hospitals across the globe.

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- ²¹ <https://data.worldbank.org/data-catalog/GDP-ranking-table>
- ²² <http://www.isqua.org/accreditation-iap/Accredited-by-ISQua>